

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Distribution of ecological groups of earthworms depending on land use

In Estonia, there are 13 species of earthworms, which are divided into three ecological groups - endogeic, epigeic, and anecic. Depending on soil cultivation, moisture, and land use, the species and groups are distributed among habitats.

Conventional farming - primarily endogeic earthworms. *Aporrectodea caliginosa* (Savigny, 1826), *Aporrectodea rosea* (Savigny, 1826), *Octolasion cyaneum* (Savigny 1826) in carbonate-rich soils and *Octolasion lacteum* (Örley 1881) in overly moist soils.

Direct seeding - with the presence of organic litter, all three ecological groups may be represented. Endogeic species include the *Aporrectodea caliginosa* (Savigny, 1826), *Aporrectodea rosea* (Savigny, 1826), *Allolobophora chlorotica* (Savigny, 1826), *Octolasion cyaneum* (Savigny 1826), and *Octolasion lacteum* (Örley

1881) in excessively wet soils. The direct seeding technique also allows for the existence of anecic species - *Lumbricus terrestris* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Aporrectodea longa* (Ude, 1885). In the field litter layer, the epigeic *Lumbricus rubellus* (Hoffmeister, 1843) can feed.

Grasslands - represented by three ecological groups. In wet grasslands, in addition to the previous species, the epigeic *Lumbricus castaneus* (Savigny, 1826) may be present. The epigeic *Eiseniella tetraedra* (Savigny, 1826) is adapted to live periodically or continuously in nutrient-rich litter of excessively moist grasslands. Grasslands are favorable for the endogeic *Allolobophora chlorotica* (Savigny, 1826).

Manure - inhabited by the common *Eisenia fetida* (Savigny, 1826).

1. Ecological groups of earthworms. Figure. Kuu, A., Shanskiy, M. 2022.

2. Common earthworm (*Lumbricus terrestris* Linnaeus). Photo Ivask, M.

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Ecological groups, land use, earthworms

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